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Report on Second EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
CPP	Core Preservation Process
CTS	CoreTrustSeal
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC EDEN	Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level
FIDELIS	Establishing a European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories
IDCC	International Digital Curation Conference.
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
LoRCAP	Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation
LTDP	Long-Term Data Preservation
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
RDA	Research Data Alliance
TDA	Trustworthy Digital Archives
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repositoryies
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

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Executive Summary

A key activity of the EOSC EDEN project is the delivery of a series of bootcamps to showcase and engage relevant stakeholders in the repository and digital preservation communities towards co-creation, awareness raising and adoption of the projects' results. The bootcamps are an activity that seeks alignment with the engagement and training activities of the FIDELIS project, a sister project to EOSC EDEN aiming to create a European network of trustworthy digital repositories.

The 2nd EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp took place on 16th February 2026 as a full-day face-to-face event in Zagreb, Croatia, co-located with the International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC26¹). The Bootcamp centred on two key outputs of the projects: the Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM), developed through FIDELIS, and the Core Preservation Processes (CPPs), developed through EOSC EDEN. The event also provided an opportunity for participants to explore the relationship between the FIDELIS Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) Network and the EOSC EDEN Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network, and to provide substantive feedback to both project teams on future priorities.

¹ <https://dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc26>

1 Introduction

The EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects started in January 2025 and were set up to be complementary in their objectives. The FIDELIS project aims to establish a European network of trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs), and represents a major part of the communities targeted by EOSC EDEN.

EOSC EDEN:

"The EOSC EDEN project (grant agreement nr. 101188015) seeks to enhance digital preservation strategies at European and National level. At its core, the project will create **a comprehensive framework** to identify what data are candidates for digital preservation. This involves **setting standards and protocols** for long-term data preservation, which will be determined through **an assessment** of data usage, quality, and the data's benefits to science and society. In addition to the framework, the EOSC EDEN project aims to **develop a model for re-appraisal of data** throughout its lifecycle"².

EOSC FIDELIS:

"The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) aims to develop a web of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and services for science in Europe. The **FIDELIS project (grant agreement no. 101188078)** will enhance **the sustainability of EOSC**, by establishing a network of healthy, vibrant and self-sustaining trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs). Within its three-year lifetime, FIDELIS project **establishes and operates** a European network of TDRs, fostering their **harmonisation and interoperability** across repositories"³.

The EOSC EDEN project is tasked with the organisation of at least three bootcamps, aiming to foster co-creation, engagement, alignment and uptake of project outputs both within the two projects but also towards external communities. The 2nd Bootcamp built upon the foundations laid at the 1st Bootcamp held in Paris in November 2025, offering more interactive sessions and a deeper focus on the two projects' primary outputs.

2 Organisation and Preparation

The organisation of the 2nd Bootcamp was again led by the EOSC EDEN project, in coordination with FIDELIS. The event was held as a full-day session on 16th February 2026 in Zagreb, Croatia, co-located with the IDCC26 conference. This arrangement was designed to maximise attendance from the international digital curation community already present at IDCC26.

The Bootcamp's overarching theme was "structuring and understanding the activities, functions, and processes of trustworthy repositories and archives." The programme comprised introductory presentations on TTRAM and CPPs, joint sessions exploring how the two frameworks interact, interactive working group exercises, and afternoon discussions focused on the alignment of the two projects' networks and community priorities.

² <https://eden-fidelis.eu/about-us>

³ *Ibid*

2.1 Delivery

On 16th February 2026, the 2nd EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp took place at the historic Esplanade Hotel in Zagreb, Croatia, one day before the IDCC26 conference. The IDCC26 theme – “AI, austerity, and authoritarianism: contemporary challenges in digital curation” – provided a fitting backdrop for discussions that touched on data sovereignty, geopolitical risks to research infrastructure, and the role of trustworthy repositories in safeguarding European research outputs.

The Bootcamp was open to all stakeholders, with a particular focus on those involved in the digital research repository and archival communities. It attracted participants from across Europe and beyond, including repository managers, data stewards, IT professionals, and policy-oriented staff from research performing organisations. The full-day format (compared to the half-day 1st Bootcamp⁴) allowed for more substantive dialogue and richer interactive exercises.

Four speakers delivered the programme: Hervé L'Hours (UK Data Service, UKDS) presented the Transparent Trustworthy Repositories Attribution Matrix (TTRAM⁵); Micky Lindlar (TIB, Germany) presented the Core Preservation Policies (CPPs⁶). Philipp Conzett (UiT, Norway) and S. Venkataraman (KNAW-DANS, Netherlands) jointly led the afternoon sessions on the two projects' respective networks, the EOSC EDEN Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network⁷ and the FIDELIS TDR Network⁸.

4 Venkataraman, S. EOSC EDEN & FIDELIS – Report on First EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp. *Zenodo* (2026).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18598810>

5 Kleemola *et al.* FIDELIS MS12 First version of TTRAM. *Zenodo* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17157958>

6 EOSC EDEN T1.2 *et al.* M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes. *Zenodo* (2025). <https://zenodo.org/records/16992452>

7 <https://eden-fidelis.eu/expert-curation-network>

8 <https://eden-fidelis.eu/fidelis-network-tdrs>

Table 1 Agenda of the 2nd EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp, 16th February, 2026, Zagreb, Croatia⁹.

Time	Topic	Presenter(s)
09:00–09:45	Welcome, project and people introductions; ice breaker / interaction (facilitate networking)	S. Venkataraman
09:45–10:15	What is TTRAM? + a quick demo	Hervé L'Hours
10:15–10:45	What is CPP? + a quick demo	Micky Lindlar
10:45–11:00	Coffee/comfort break	
11:00–11:30	How do TTRAM and CPP relate and interact? How to use both as a repository	Hervé L'Hours, Micky Lindlar
11:30–12:00	Interactive work with the two models; discussion and feedback	Moderated by: Hervé L'Hours, Micky Lindlar
12:00–13:00	Lunch break	
13:00–13:30	FIDELIS and EOSC EDEN networks: their alignment and purpose	S. Venkataraman, Philipp Conzett
13:30–14:15	Discussion: different perspectives and feedback on the networks, their usability, etc.	Moderated by: Philipp Conzett, S. Venkataraman
14:15–14:30	Coffee/comfort break	
14:30–15:00	More interactive work with the models: next steps	All
15:00–15:45	Ask input: what should be done/created by EDEN/FIDELIS? Guidance, tools, support, etc.	All
15:45–16:00	Wrap-up	S. Venkataraman

2.2 Key Findings and Discussions

The following subsections distil the key themes, discussions and feedback that emerged across the Bootcamp sessions, drawn from the shared notes recorded by participants on the day.

2.2.1 TTRAM

Hervé L'Hours introduced TTRAM as a framework for understanding and communicating repository practices, emphasising from the outset that it is not an assessment tool and is not intended to judge respondents for “wrong answers”. TTRAM is designed to support alignment and self-reflection rather than certification, and should be seen as a comprehensive “table of contents” that repositories can use to navigate and drill into areas relevant to their context.

Key points from the session and subsequent discussion included the following:

- TTRAM uses the LoRCAP (Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation) framework from CoreTrustSeal (CTS¹⁰), addressing the recognised problem that the terms are used inconsistently across contexts. Participants were encouraged to engage with those parts of TTRAM most applicable to their organisation, as not all activities and functions will be relevant to every repository. Future work is planned to develop “profiles” of TTRAM - for example, a CTS profile - which would lower the barrier to entry for repositories approaching the framework for the first time. NB. The TTRAM spreadsheet is very large and does not need to be filled in completely - only the locally relevant parts that are useful for an organisation should be filled in.
- Ultimately, this is about where researchers' needs must be considered including how they could/should deposit their data and how they can find the right repository for their needs.
- The concept of trust transitivity was highlighted: repositories must consider their relationships with third-party suppliers as part of their trustworthiness claims. Interoperability was identified as a widely used but underdeveloped concept within the repository community.
- Discussions also touched on TTRAM's role in helping different stakeholder groups - researchers, publishers, funders and repository operators - align their expectations. Participants noted that one of the primary functions of the FIDELIS TDR Network (see below) should be advocacy and helping the community speak with a shared voice to these different audiences.

2.2.2 CPPs

Micky Lindlar presented CPPs as a practically oriented complement to existing standards, noting that while standards typically focus on what needs to be done, CPPs address the what, why and how of each process. CPPs are structured as helpful “how-to” descriptions that repositories can use to build incrementally towards becoming a Trustworthy Digital Archive (TDA).

¹⁰<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

Three layers of data quality were introduced as underpinning the CPP framework: contextual data quality (the reasons for preserving something), technical data quality (file formats, structures and coding), and metadata quality (everything that makes data understandable and manageable over time). Participants noted that digital preservation is not solely a long-term concern - good data quality practices are equally important at the point of deposit.

A number of practical clarifications emerged from discussions:

- CPPs are more granular and implementation-focused than the Open Archival Information System (OAIS¹¹), and are oriented specifically towards the digital environment.
- A repository or archive can be both a TDA and a TDR, as these are roles rather than mutually exclusive institutional categories.
- Policies need not exist as formal documents - what matters is that a decision was made, by whom, and when, and that the impacts are understood.

Participants requested more worked examples and reference implementations within the CPP documentation. This was acknowledged as a useful area for future collaboration between the two projects.

The CPP milestone document (*EOSC EDEN T1.2 et al. (2025) M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes*, Zenodo) was referenced as the authoritative source for mappings between CPPs and other frameworks¹².

11 <http://www.oais.info/>

12 EOSC EDEN T1.2 et al. (2025) M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/16992452>

2.2.3 Relating TTRAM and CPPs in Practice

A joint session led by Hervé L'Hours and Micky Lindlar explored how TTRAM and CPPs relate to one another and how a repository might use both together. The session introduced a simplified three-stage framework - *Inputs, Planning, and Implementation* - to help participants structure their thinking without limiting discussion.

Working in small groups, participants applied TTRAM and CPPs to their own institutional contexts, focusing on one of three areas: (i) external and internal factors that shape inputs (legal, ethical, policy and technological constraints); (ii) planning workflows that take those inputs into account; or (iii) implementing operational workflows. Those who preferred a holistic approach were also accommodated.

The breakout discussions revealed several recurring themes across groups:

- On the inputs side, legal and regulatory requirements - such as national mandates to retain research data for a minimum of ten years - were cited across multiple jurisdictions, including Sweden and the Czech Republic, and also in Japan. Participants noted that legal obligations to retain data do not necessarily entail an obligation to share it, and that discipline-specific factors (including the scale of datasets, sensitivity, and the provenance of AI-generated components) must inform appraisal decisions. Legacy data - data already held in repositories without sufficient documentation or rights information - was identified as a persistent practical challenge.
- On the planning side, participants highlighted TTRAM attribute AF04 (Digital Object Management: Deposit and Appraisal) and CPP-022 (Significant Properties Definition), CPP-017 (Disposal) and CPP-019 (Data Quality Assessment) as particularly relevant entry points. The importance of engaging researchers early - ideally at the data management plan stage - was stressed, as was the recognition that long-term preservation is resource-intensive and that automation (for example, automated flagging of file formats at risk) could significantly reduce the burden on repository staff.
- At the implementation level, participants drew on national examples to illustrate different models. In Finland, the Finnish Social Science Data Archive (FSD) is responsible for curation and reusability, while bit-level preservation is handled by the national service CSC. This separation of roles was seen as instructive for thinking about how repositories and preservation infrastructures might collaborate more systematically.

2.2.4 FIDELIS and EOSC EDEN Networks

The afternoon session, led by Philipp Conzett and S. Venkataraman, presented the two projects' respective networks and invited participants to discuss their relationship, purpose and future governance.

The FIDELIS TDR Network, which had surpassed its initial membership target of 60 repositories at the time of the 1st Bootcamp, was described as continuing to grow and to investigate pathways towards becoming a self-sustaining entity beyond the lifetime of the projects. The EOSC EDEN Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network (hereafter referred to as the EDEN Curation Network) was introduced as a distinct but complementary initiative, focused on bringing together

individuals with expertise in data curation and long-term preservation - who may or may not be affiliated with a repository. At a workshop organised at KU Leuven in October 2025, curation and digital preservation experts discussed and provided feedback on the creation of the EDEN Curation Network¹³.

Discussion explored whether, and how, the two networks might align. Participants questioned whether the repository community needs yet another network alongside existing bodies such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA¹⁴) and CTS, and asked whether a revitalised RDA working group model - or even a Community of Practice - might serve the same purpose more efficiently. The question of added value was raised directly: repositories and their staff will engage with a network only if membership offers something tangible.

Several suggestions emerged. The idea of linking TDR Network membership to existing certifications - such that repositories holding CTS, Nestor or ISO certification would automatically qualify - was proposed as a way of establishing a clear threshold of trustworthiness without creating a new certification regime. Participants also raised the possibility of the TDR Network acting as a neutral custodian for key outputs from EU-funded projects, addressing the widely acknowledged problem that valuable community resources generated through time-limited projects often lack a stable long-term home. The concept of peer-to-peer learning, mentoring programmes and show-and-tell sessions was welcomed as a concrete benefit that a network could offer, and the potential use of existing funding mechanisms such as Erasmus exchanges for knowledge-sharing between institutions was noted.

¹³ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/blog/1st-eosc-eden-curation-workshop-leuven-belgium-gathering-experts-build-european-curation-and>

¹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

The role of IT professionals was highlighted as an important and underserved constituency: bridging the gap between curation experts and institutional IT departments - who often manage the infrastructure on which preservation depends - was identified as a priority for both the TDR Network and the EDEN Curation Network's training activities.

Clarification was provided that the EDEN Curation Network working groups are open to contributors from outside the two projects, and that collaboration with other EOSC-related projects - such as Skills4EOSC¹⁵ and OSCARS¹⁶ - would be kept in mind as the network develops.

2.2.5 What should EDEN/FIDELIS create and deliver?

The penultimate session invited participants to reflect more broadly on what the two projects should prioritise in terms of outputs, tools and guidance. Several concrete suggestions were made.

There was a strong appetite for curated templates and registries - participants noted that while a large body of documentation about curation and preservation already exists, it is dispersed and difficult to navigate. A single, well-maintained registry or knowledge base - a "single source of truth" - was seen as highly valuable. The Canadian Borealis CTS Certification Documentation Suite was cited as an instructive example of a network of expert groups collaborating to produce common documentation.

Participants also called for more practical worked examples within both TTRAM and the CPP documentation, and for clearer guidance on how to engage the different audiences involved in preservation decisions: IT staff, legal advisors, data stewards and researchers. A train-the-trainers model was suggested as a scalable approach to building capacity across institutions. Providing researchers with credit or other incentives for supplying richer metadata at the point of deposit was proposed as a way to address the persistent problem of variable metadata quality.

Finally, participants flagged the growing landscape of repositories as a systemic challenge: rather than proliferating new repositories, the community might benefit from clearer guidance on when data should be migrated to a specialised trustworthy repository after an initial retention period, and what criteria should govern that decision.

3 Conclusions and next steps

The 2nd EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp demonstrated growing community engagement with the outputs of both projects. The full-day format, combined with the co-location alongside IDCC26, succeeded in attracting a broad and internationally diverse audience and created the conditions for substantive, practically grounded dialogue.

The sessions on TTRAM and CPPs confirmed that both frameworks are being received as useful and actionable tools by the repository and archival communities, while also highlighting areas where further development - in particular, more worked examples, profiles and reference implementations - would enhance their usability. The afternoon discussions on the two networks

¹⁵ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://oscars-project.eu/>

surfaced important questions about governance, sustainability, added value and the relationship between project-based outputs and the long-term needs of the community. At the time of writing, the team behind the CPPs have also released a web tool for interactively visualising them¹⁷. This tool allows users to inspect the relationships between them and to drill down into their individual descriptions and respective Zenodo entries.

Project partners involved in engagement, outreach and training are actively taking forward the feedback received at this Bootcamp to inform the further development of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS outputs. The iterative model of showcasing and refining outputs at successive Bootcamps continues to serve as an effective mechanism for co-creation with the key target communities.

3.1 Next Bootcamp

Planning for the 3rd EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp is already underway. The two projects will reach their mid-point in summer 2026, and the 3rd Bootcamp will reflect this milestone by presenting a more comprehensive review of outputs generated to date and soliciting community feedback to inform the final year of the projects' activities. The 3rd Bootcamp will be at the RDA P27 conference in London¹⁸ and will be on the day before the conference itself, on 5th October 2026 and will again be a full-day format. Speakers and an agenda are being drafted and will be published by the summer 2026.

¹⁷ <https://cpp.fd-dev.csc.fi/>

¹⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/p27/>